

Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting (FGM/C) and Breast Ironing: Body Alterations as Violation of Right to Female Body Autonomy

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Abstract

The paper attempts to explore the connection between two controversial body alterations in terms of the control of female body by patriarchy and the subjugation of females in the name of culture and tradition. The controversial body alterations namely Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting (FGM/C) and Breast Ironing lead to many health complications including long term or short term health issues. The parents who are unaware of the consequences let their daughters undergo the procedures for social acceptance. Mostly FGM/C is done to protect the virginity and to control sexual desires. Breast ironing is done to reduce the men getting sexually attracted to girls/women. With reference to the abolition of foot binding, and the need to create an understanding of their right for bodily integrity and the need to protect women from any such subjugations.

Keywords: control of female body, Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting, Breast Ironing, subjugations, bodily integrity.

Introduction

“ . . . gender is not to culture as sex is to nature; gender is also the discursive/cultural means by which “sexed nature” or “a natural sex” is produced and established as “prediscursive,” prior to culture, a politically neutral surface on which culture acts.”

- Judith Butler, *Gender Trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity*, 1999.

Violence against women has been in existence for a long time irrespective of their age, class, caste and education. The United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women which is also known as UN Women claims that 35% of women around the globe have underwent some form of physical and/or sexual violence or harassment and, in some national studies, almost 70% of women have faced physical and/or sexual abuse. Around 71% of human trafficking victims are adult women and girls and approximately three out of four those trafficked women and girls are abducted for sexual exploitation (“Facts and figures”, 2018).

The control of female body by patriarchal societies is one of the repeatedly discussed topics in the field of academic and legal

discourses. The paper attempts to explore the two important types of body alteration/modification which are done for non-therapeutic reasons namely Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting (FGM/C) and Breast Ironing. These two controversial body modifications which are originated in Africa have become highly debated topics in legal and medical fields as they are seen as threat to bodily integrity and human rights.

Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting (FGM/C)

In some cultures, FGM/C is seen as “rite of passage into adulthood that was carried out when girls were of pre-pubescent age” (Costello, 2018, p. 36). The United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF) (2013) reports Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting as “a range of practices involving the complete or partial removal or alteration of the external genitalia for nonmedical reasons” (p. 6). World Health Organisation has categorised the procedures that comes under the umbrella term in 2008. The following categories are taken from the interagency statement entitled Eliminating female genital mutilation: An Interagency Statement UNAIDS, UNDP, UNECA, UNESCO, UNFPA, UNHCHR, UNHCR, UNICEF, UNIFEM, WHO and all these types are considered by these agencies as “a harmful practice and a violation of the human rights of girls and women” (World Health Organisation, 2008, p. 8)

Type I: “Partial or total removal of the clitoris and/or the prepuce (clitoridectomy)” (World Health Organization, 2008, p. 4).

Type II: “Partial or total removal of the clitoris and the labia minora, with or without excision of the labia majora (excision)” (World Health Organization, 2008, p. 4).

Type III: “Narrowing of the vaginal orifice with creation of a covering seal by cutting and appositioning the labia minora and/or the labia majora, with or without excision of the clitoris (infibulation)” (World Health Organization, 2008, p. 4).

Type IV: “All other harmful procedures to the female genitalia for non-medical purposes, for example: pricking, piercing, incising, scraping and cauterization” (World Health Organization, 2008, p. 4).

Mostly, girls of four to fourteen years are affected and it is revealed that infants are also made to undergo the procedure (Toubia, 1994, p. 712). Most of the times, the ones who perform the procedures are traditional circumcisers, old women, birth attendants, women from the same locality or the women the family (World Health Organization, 2018; Momoh, 2010, p. 12; Whitehorn, Ayonrinde, & Maingay, 2002, p.163). In most cases, the tools used for the procedures are non-sterile like razor blades. In addition to this, the girls or women who undergo the procedure are not given any kind of anaesthesia. In some places, herbs, ash and commixture of cow dung are used as the ingredients used to heal the women (Whitehorn et al., 2002, p. 163).

World Health Organisation states that the girls and women do not get any kind of health benefits rather they experience a lot of health issues as the procedures include “removing and damaging healthy and normal female genital tissue, and interferes with the natural functions of girls’ and women’s bodies” (World Health Organization, 2018). the following health issues are faced by those who undergo FGM/C as reported by WHO - “severe pain”, “excessive bleeding”, “genital tissue swelling”, “infections”, “urinary problems”, “wound healing problems”, “shock”, “death”, etc. (World Health Organization, 2018). The following are long term health complications listed by WHO - “urinary problems”, “vaginal problems”, “menstrual problems”, “sexual problems”, “increased risk of childbirth complications”, etc. The girls and women who undergo FGM/C may suffer from many psychological health complications like “depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, low self-esteem, etc.” (World Health Organization, 2018).

In a shocking report released by United Nation's Children's Fund in 2016, it has been revealed that around two hundred million girls and women in 30 countries have undergone some form of FGM/C (United Nations Children's Fund, 2016). FGM/C is closely connected with culture, belief of family, gender, marriage and, most importantly, "proper sexual behaviour" (Costello, 2018, p. 35). The practice is connected with the concepts of "femininity, chastity and modesty" and it is believed to control women's sexual desire (Costello, 2018, p. 35). The girls/women who undergo the procedures are believed to be "clean" and "beautiful" (Costello, 2018, p. 36). Depending on the higher rate of prevalence in some countries, religion also plays an important role (United Nations Children's Fund, 2005, p. 17). Sometimes, the practice is seen to be connected with Islam as some Islamic groups follow this practice in particular but research shows that people of non-Islamic religious groups also follow the practice (United Nations Children's Fund, 2013, p. 69).

Breast Ironing

"If society has been silent about it up to now is because, like other harmful practices done to women such as female genital mutilation, it was thought to be good for the girl...even the victims themselves thought it was good for them." (Flavien Ndonko, Anthropologist and local representative of German Development Agency GTZ) (as cited in Ngunshi, 2011, p. 3).

The practice of 'breast ironing' is sometimes known as 'breast flattening' (Tapscott, 2012, p. i). Rebecca Tapscott defines breast flattening as "a practice whereby an object is used to massage, pound, or press the breasts flat, is common in Cameroon and throughout West Africa" (2012, p. 1). Girls of eight to twelve years old are affected by this practice as this is the period when girls develop breasts naturally (Tapscott, 2012, p. i, 1). The German Society for International Cooperation (known as GIZ) was the first international organisation to highlight breast ironing as "a practice harmful for girl children" (Tapscott, 2012, p. 1). In her study, BAWE Rosaline Ngunshi (2011) regards the practice as a form of "family violence" and further categorises it as "female to female" (p. 7).

In a study conducted under the guidance of Dr. Flavien Ndonko, a number of 5, 661 girls and women from ten regions of Cameroon (aged between 10 and 82) were questioned of the topics "breast ironing", "rape" and "incest" and it was found out that almost a "quarter" of them from Cameroon had experienced breast flattening one way or the other (Tapscott, 2012, 1). The most shocking thing is that it is performed "most often by the girl's own mother (nearly 60% of the time), but also by a nurse or caretaker, aunt, older sister, grandmother, the girl herself and, in a minority of cases, by a traditional healer, father, brother, cousin, friend, or neighbor" (Tapscott, 2012, 1).

Methods used to flatten the breasts include "a grinding stone, a wooden pestle, a spatula or broom, a belt to tie or bind the breasts flat, leaves thought to have special medicinal or healing qualities, napkins, plantain peels, stones, fruit pits, coconut shells, salt, ice, and others" (Tapscott, 2012, p. 6). Some of the possible side effects are "an immediate delay or halting of breast growth swelling, burning, irritation, pimples on the breasts, abscesses, fever, extreme pain, a long-term overgrowth of one or both breasts or failure for one or both breasts to grow, difficulty to breast-feed, scarring, and breast cancer" (Tapscott, 2012, p.13). Sometimes, an object like a wooden pestle is heated in the fire and the hot pestle is pressed/massaged/pounded on the breasts. Tapscott cites that the most important motivation behind breast flattening as the "growing social need to discourage pre-marital sexual activity in an environment where females, particularly girls and young women, have limited agency" (2012, p. 18). Many social groups in Cameroon are "partilineal" and the women have no control in their marital unions (Tapscott, 2012, p. 18).

Prevalence of Child marriages, polygamy and bride wealth have made women to be dependent on their male guardians. Tapscott writes that many men of Cameroon assume that the girl who shows signs of physical growth as “ripe for sex” (Tapscott, 2012, 18, 23). Without any consideration for the age and consent of the girl or women, “men feel entitled to aggressively pursue any physically mature woman” (Tapscott, 2012, 23). It has been revealed that the practice of breast ironing is being followed among the people settled in UK from some African countries and it is believed that around one thousand girls and women have been affected by the practice (Lazareva, 2019).

The Need for Change

None of the countries in the world are free from occurrence of traumatic events but some researchers like So’Nia L. Gilkey and Theresa Kaijage consider Africa as “the world’s foremost locus for the experience of trauma” in accordance with the World Health Organization report in 2005 (as cited in Gilkey, 2012, pp. 16). The causes of physical and mental trauma in Africa, as found in researches, are “civil wars, ethnic conflict, poverty, historical consequences of colonialism, cultural traditions, human rights abuses, and the ongoing subjugation and marginalization of women and girls” (as cited in Gilkey, 2012, pp. 16). As we can see in any other country, some of the traditional practices, customs human rights abuses, war and poverty affects the most vulnerable group, women and children, in a sever way (pp. 16). Understanding the trauma of African women should start with understanding the values, morals, worldviews and belief structures of a community.

To bring change, instead of blaming the parents, it is important to learn how the culture and belief system of a community works. Ellen Gruenbaum, an American anthropologist, writes:

Female circumcision practices are deeply entwined with ethnic identity wherever they are found. Understanding this should provide an important insight into the tenacity of the practice and people’s resistance to change efforts, and it can help to explain why the practice may even spread in certain situations” (as cited in United Nations Children’s Fund, 2005, pp. 11).

Even though many international conventions have been passed against harmful traditional practices, they are still followed secretly. The girls/women who are not circumcised are considered to be ineligible for marriage and are stigmatised and the families are excommunicated (Costello, 2018, pp. 36). Sensitizing elders in family towards the practices is as important as educating the younger generation and they can be used as a powerful, influential source of change. Though the voluntary organisations are working to end the practice, it is important for the governments to take steps like introducing a strong national law and reviewing the existing conventions for the eradication of the practices. Interagency alliance of different ministries that work for children’s health, education, human rights, women rights, etc. can bring a greater change in a larger scale. The coalition of government and non-government agencies can provide outreach and awareness programs for religious leaders, traditional practitioners, physicians, people living in rural areas and younger generation.

Gerry Mackie, in “Ending Footbinding and Infibulation: A Convention Account” proposes that the practice of FGM/C can be ended with pledge associations. Same method can be used for breast ironing too. The practice of footbinding of women in China was ended by such associations in the beginning of twentieth century. The parents should be informed of the advantages of the intact genitals and disadvantages of FGM/C and breast ironing and Associations of parents who are opposing the practices should be formed. They should take a pledge not to let their daughters undergo the procedures. In China, the communities which practiced the footbinding abandoned the practice slowly, with the influence of those who joined the pledge associations (Mackie, 1996, 1001, 1015). Mackie’s technique can be used to bring community level change and through combining it with new innovative methods, the practice can gradually wiped out from all nations.

Conclusion

Any kind of surgeries done on the human body, without an individual's consent, for non-therapeutic reasons, is a violation of the bodily integrity of children of all sexes and women. It should also be considered as a gender-based violence and no one has the right to influence the physical integrity of another person in terms of culture and religion. Assuming the sexual desires of female are uncontrollable and therefore they need to be restricted with surgeries on female sexual organ is a serious contravention to the dignity of women. Considering any girl/woman who is physically matured as desirable for sex is obvious threat to the protection of girls/women. To eradicate the practices, there is a need for viable strategies that makes it easier to work with the community, with their full involvement in the process.

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